

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP) CREATED FOR THE PROJECT:

Structure-function studies of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Type VI Secretion System toxins (T6SS- TOXINS)

This DMP is based on the "Plan Estatal" template provided by Plan Estatal (*Agencia Estatal de Investigación*), and has been created with the assistance of the tool "eiNa DMP" (<https://dmp.csuc.cat>).

Creator: David ALBESA-JOVÉ

Affiliation: Instituto Biofisika – Fundación Biofísica Bizkaia

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1. DATA SUMMARY

Experimental data will be collected in order to meet our objectives of the Project. In particular, the following data might be generated:

Biophysical data: ITC, SPR, flow cytometry, SAXS data, structure factors from X-ray diffraction, cryo-EM maps and micrographs, atomic coordinates of protein structures.

In vitro data: enzymatic data, SDS-PAGES, Mass Spectrometry data, N-terminal Edman sequencing data.

In vivo data: bacterial competition data, toxicity data, DNA/RNA-sequencing data, ELISA data, proteomic data.

1.A PURPOSE OF THE DATA COLLECTION/GENERATION AND ITS RELATION TO THE OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT

The purpose of collecting and making available the data is to support the scientific publications' credibility and quality. Ease the exchange of data within the research team and collaborators. Permit follow-up projects and further generations of students to build upon existing data sets, validate the results, and document the improvement of materials and production techniques in a verifiable manner. This approach will ensure a durable impact of this MICINN funded Project beyond the project period.

The objective of the Project is to advance our understanding of T6SS effectors of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Managed collection and publication of the data shall help establish a durable library of results that can help document the performance evolution across several years and permit other researchers to validate the results independently.

1.B TYPES AND FORMATS OF DATA THAT WILL BE GENERATED/COLLECTED

The majority of the data will be in ASCII (American Standard Code for Information Interchange), data files, e.g. comma-separated variable (CSV) format, which can be imported into rich-text files for word-processing or spreadsheets. If specialised software is used, then information about free readers will be provided. Data will be generated in the following formats:

1. Videos: mp4
2. Graphics: tiff, pdf
3. Tables: ODS, CSV, TXT
4. Text: docx, pdf
5. Crystallographic Information Files: CIF
6. Cryo-EM maps: MRC
7. Cryo-EM micrographs: TIFF, MRC

The openly accessible data will be the comprehensive data sets of characterised samples used to create the figures and plots in scientific publications. In this way, other researchers can compare their results easier, and other results, including historical data, can be produced quicker. Also, raw images and measurement data files as provided by the measurement instruments will be stored **on a project-internal data storage platform**. For all published

files, a record file with a track change will be included (author, contact information, status, version, change reason and date, description of contents, title, origin of the data including a brief description of the measurement and experiment setup). This record file will be provided in a separate metadata file for each characterisation action called METADATA.ODS.

1.C USE OF EXISTING DATA

Some of the Project's tasks will use existing data in CIF format available in the Protein Data bank (<https://www.rcsb.org/>). These data will be used for tasks that involve structural determination by X-ray crystallography, or for comparison.

1.D ORIGIN OF THE DATA

The data stem from experiments and measurement campaigns performed by the research team at the beneficiary institute and technical facilities available to the Project.

1.E EXPECTED SIZE OF THE DATA

The size of the data is today not known. Initial experience with storing results from different kind of measurements will permit revising this initial data management plan. The main relevant data sizes will stem from images such as cryo-electron microscopy recordings stored in high-resolution images, which have a total data set size for a single sample characterisation in the order of 5-15 TB.

1.F DATA UTILITY: TO WHOM WILL IT BE USEFUL

Given the novelty and originality of the Project, the data will be useful for:

1. Other research groups working on the following topics: bacterial secretion systems, bacterial pathogenesis, bacterial toxins.
2. Within the research team and collaborators: The data sets will be shared within the research team and collaborators as the working baseline to produce the scientific publications, to verify and validate the results through repeated experiments at different locations and as a baseline for a comprehensive documentation of evaluation of the project performance and impact.
3. Beyond the research team and collaborators: Independent researchers can use the data to understand better the contents and conclusions of the scientific publications, which base their findings on the data. Furthermore, independent researchers can use the files to produce figures and publications, showing comparisons of their results and our results. Scientists can also use the data files to repeat the experiments and measurements to verify and validate our research.
4. This project's data will be useful for users and institutions considering similar technologies in their research.
5. Finally, scientific writers and the press may also use the data sets to produce high-quality infographics, demonstrating the technology's impact potentials.

2. FAIR DATA

2.1.A DISCOVERABILITY AND IDENTIFIABILITY OF DATA PRODUCED

1. The structural data generated will be deposited in publicly available databases, which provides a unique URL to access the data. Data will be made available after acceptance of corresponding publications. The public structural databases used will be: The Protein Data Bank (<https://www.rcsb.org/>); the Electron Microscopy Data Bank (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/emdb/>); the Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/empair/>) and the Small Angle Scattering Biological Databank (<https://www.sasbdb.org/>). These repositories assign DOIs for persistent identification and citability of the datasets.
2. The remaining of the data will be deposited into CERN's Data Centre ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org/>).

2.1.B NAMING CONVENTIONS

1. The public structural databases (RCSB, EMDB, EMPIAR and SASBDB) generate a unique identifier for each entry, which will be cited in the corresponding publication.
2. Data files deposited in ZENODO will be associated to a unique DOI number that ZENODO generates. This ZENODO DOI will be cited in the corresponding publication.

2.1.C USE OF SEARCH KEYWORDS TO OPTIMISE POSSIBILITIES FOR REUSE

1. All open project results deposited in ZENODO will provide search keywords together with their metadata. Keywords for open data will be selected from controlled vocabularies suitable for the specific type of data.

2.1.D APPROACH THAT WILL BE USED FOR VERSION TRACKING

1. Version control mechanisms should be established and documented before any data are collected or generated.
2. All open datasets, and publications deposited in the ZENODO repository will use DOI versioning. DOI versioning allows updating a dataset after it has been published and cites either a specific version of a dataset or all versions of a dataset.

2.1.E WHAT METADATA WILL BE CREATED

1. **Structural databases:** the metadata standard used to describe the structural datasets will be the mmCIF (macromolecular Crystallographic Information File). mmCIF standard is a flexible and extensible tag-value format for representing macromolecular structural data. Notably, the mmCIF is a commonly used standard in structural biology. These metadata are created manually by depositors in the deposit form.
2. **ZENDO repository:** The metadata standard used to describe the datasets will be the Dublin Core Schema. It is a flexible and common used standard and is also the one adopted by the European OpenAIRE repository. The datasets will be interoperable as Zenodo's basic metadata requirement (i.e. 1) description, 2) creator/ownership, 3) access, 4) lifecycle, 5) persistent identifiers) is compliant with the recommended standards used by DataCite (<https://search.datacite.org/>), OpenAIRE (<https://www.base-search.net/>), and Dublin Core Schema.

2.2 DATA ACCESS

2.2.A WHICH DATA PRODUCED IN THE PROJECT WILL BE MADE OPENLY AVAILABLE AS THE DEFAULT

All of the data associated with scientific publications will be made openly available as the default unless there is a specific reason not to publish the data.

The following data will not be made publicly available:

- Data obtained with third parties' permission, but the third parties have not agreed to make the data publicly available.
- Data that discloses the identity of a manufacturer.
- Data that compromises the protection of a partner(s) intellectual property. The detail of data made available will also be considered; for example, pre-processed data will not be provided unless there is an apparent reason for doing so.

2.2.B HOW THE DATA WILL BE MADE AVAILABLE

Once processing, quality control, organisation, analysis and publication are complete, the data will be made accessible by deposition in open access structural databases and repositories indicated in section 2.1.A.

2.2.C WHAT METHODS OR SOFTWARE TOOLS ARE NEEDED TO ACCESS THE DATA

Web browser and application programming interfaces (API) offered by these storage systems, complemented by free customised tools developed by users and the scientific community.

2.2.D SOFTWARE DOCUMENTATION NEEDED TO ACCESS THE DATA

Standard publicly available software will be used where possible. However, if specialist software tools are developed, a short text file (e.g. ASCII) will be provided with the data file to explain the software required.

2.2.E SOFTWARE AVAILABILITY NEEDED TO ACCESS THE DATA

The majority of the software programmes are available as commercial products or as freeware.

2.2.F WHERE THE DATA, ASSOCIATED METADATA, AND DOCUMENTATION WILL BE DEPOSITED

The data and associated metadata, documentation and code will either be deposited in the open access repository called ZENODO or in structural databases indicated in section 2.1.A.

2.2.G APPROPRIATE ARRANGEMENTS IN PLACE WITH THE REPOSITORIES

We have extensive experience with data deposition in the structural databases indicated in section 2.1. Furthermore, we have already generated an account and explored the appropriate arrangements with ZENODO. The first publication we have deposited in ZENODO is this Data Management Plan (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4305714)

2.2.H HOW ACCESS WILL BE PROVIDED IF THERE ARE RESTRICTIONS ON USE

There are no restrictions on using the published data, but users will be required to acknowledge our Project and the data source in any resulting publications.

2.2.I DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE

Because of the project's objectives is the generation of knowledge, and therefore, data produced by the Project will be available, there is no need for a data access committee.

2.2.J CONDITIONS FOR ACCESS

ZENODO, RCSB, EMBD and SASDB provide well-described conditions for access (see <http://about.zenodo.org/policies/>, <https://www.rcsb.org/pages/usage-policy>, <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/emdb/policies.html>, <https://www.sasbdb.org/aboutSASBDB/>

2.2.K IDENTITY OF THE PERSON ACCESSING THE DATA

Identity of the person accessing the data will not be directly ascertained. However, we expect users to follow the standard norms of scientific citation, and use of the data in this context will be tracked through scientific citation.

2.3. WHAT DATA AND METADATA VOCABULARIES, STANDARDS OR METHODOLOGIES WILL BE USED TO FACILITATE INTEROPERABILITY

The data produced in the Project will be interoperable as the datasets will adhere to standardised formats: ASCII, txt, csv, xml, tiff, mmCIF. If MS Office, pdf viewer or image viewer cannot be used, a text (ASCII) file will be provided with the dataset that explains where a free reader can be obtained.

2.3.B USE OF STANDARD VOCABULARY FOR ALL DATA TYPES TO ALLOW INTER-DISCIPLINARY INTEROPERABILITY

Structural data will use the mmCIF standard vocabulary; a dictionary is available at <http://mmcif.wwpdb.org> for data interpretation. The non-structural data will use a descriptive vocabulary to allow easy inter-disciplinary interoperability.

2.4.A HOW THE DATA WILL BE LICENCED TO PERMIT THE WIDEST REUSE POSSIBLE

Wherever possible, the data will be shared right after publication following the Creative Commons 4.0 International License with Attribution (CC4BY).

2.4.B WHEN THE DATA WILL BE MADE AVAILABLE FOR REUSE

The data will remain reusable after the project's end by anyone interested in it, with no access or time restrictions.

2.4.C USE OF DATA BY THIRD PARTIES

Each archived data set will have its permanent repository ID and will be easily accessible. We expect most of the data generated to be made available without restrictions, and only datasets subject to IPR and confidentiality issues will be restricted. When this applies, we will make agreements based on the individual datasets. The PI will approve requests for the use of the data by externals of the Project.

2.4.D DATA QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCESSES

Different measures ensure the data quality. These include validation of the sample, replication and comparison with similar studies and control of systematic distortion. Furthermore, structural data is externally validated by the structural databases' curators where the data will be deposited.

2.4.E LENGTH OF TIME FOR WHICH THE DATA WILL REMAIN REUSABLE

The data deposited in ZENODO will remain reusable until they discontinue the dataset(s) (i.e. warranted for a minimum of 20 years).

The data deposited in the structural databases will remain reusable indefinitely.

3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

3.A ESTIMATED COSTS FOR MAKING THE DATA FAIR

There are no costs associated to the described mechanisms to make the database FAIR and long term preserved.

3.B SPECIFY HOW WILL BE COVERED

Internal costs for keeping the raw data and a backup of available data in FAIR repositories will be covered at the local hosting institute as a part of the standard network system maintenance.

3.C RESPONSIBLE FOR DATA MANAGEMENT IN THE PROJECT

The PI has the ultimate responsibility for the data management in the Project. The research team will be responsible for organising data backup and storage, data archiving, and depositing the data within the repositories (ZENODO and structural databases).

3.D RESOURCES FOR LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

There are no costs associated with the long-term preservation of the data in ZENODO and structural databases.

4. DATA SECURITY

4.A DATA RECOVERY, SECURE STORAGE AND TRANSFER OF SENSITIVE DATA

Raw data collected will be stored on the University's EHUstorage service. The EHUstorage service Agreement includes Terms and Conditions that are compliant with EU Data Protection Law and the National Bioethics Committee rules and regulations. Only researchers working for the Project will have access to the data, using their username and passwords to access the files. The research group will also keep a backup copy on a hard-disk stored in the Instituto Biofisika Room 0B5. Only the Principal Investigator for the Project will have access to the hard-disk. Safety is ensured for the building and the room with 24-hour security.

The data submitted to the public ZENODO repository and structural databases will provide additional security. These services produce multiple replicas in a distributed file system which is backed up on a nightly basis. The data will be safely stored in ZENODO open access repository, is working towards ISO certification of the organisational and technical infrastructure, which ZENODO relies on for long-term preservation (<https://blogs.openaire.eu/?p=1485>).

5. ETHICAL ASPECTS

5.A ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT MAY AFFECT THE COLLECTION AND SHARING OF DATA

All the activities carried out under the Project comply with ethical principles and relevant national, EU and international legislation, for example, the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention on Human Rights. The tasks of our project only concern basic research activities and does not involve humans or animals.

6. OTHER ISSUES

6.A OTHER NATIONAL/FUNDER/SECTORIAL/DEPARTMENTAL PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT THAT WILL BE USED

The Project will adhere to the University of the Basque Country's commitment to ensuring FAIR and Open data: <https://www.ehu.es/es/web/biblioteca/upv/ehuaren-politika-sarbide-irekirako>

7. FURTHER SUPPORT IN DEVELOPING THIS DMP

7.A RESOURCES USED TO DEVELOP THIS DMP

This DMP is based on the "Plan Estatal" template provided by the *Agencia Estatal de Investigación*. The DMP has been created with the tool "eiNa DMP" (<https://dmp.csuc.cat>).